

Methods for Early Detection and Treatment of Chronic Bronchitis

Tolmasov Ruzibek Tolmasovich

Tashkent Medical Academy, Department of Human Anatomy and OSTA
ruzibektolmasov@gmail.com

Sobirjonova Munavvarxon Bakhtiyorjon qizi

Tashkent Medical Academy, A student of the Faculty of Medicine No. 2 of the
baxtiyorovna1003@gmail.com

Abstract: This article examines the importance of early detection and treatment of chronic bronchitis, as well as the structure of the bronchi. Chronic bronchitis is a long-term inflammation of the bronchial tubes, characterized by persistent cough and phlegm production. If chronic bronchitis is not diagnosed early, the patient's condition will gradually worsen. For example, breathing difficulties may increase. In this case, oxygen deficiency and sometimes lung failure may occur. Also, if necessary medical treatment is not carried out, chronic bronchitis can progress to chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), pulmonary hypertension and cardiovascular disease. In the early stages of the disease, symptoms may not be noticeable, so early detection is very important to slow down the progressive damage to the lungs and improve the patient's quality of life.

Keywords: bronchi, chronic bronchitis, spirometry, chronic obstructive bronchitis, tachycardia, pulmonary emphysema, corticosteroids, broncholytics.

Introduction: Bronchi - *the bronchus is an organ that conducts* air from the trachea to the alveoli of the lungs, ensures its reverse direction, and cleans the air from harmful particles. The wall of the bronchus consists of a mucous membrane - a layer that traps dust and microbes, smooth muscle fibers, and cartilage and connective tissue. The bronchi are one of the important components of the respiratory system and are structured as follows:

- Main bronchi – (*bronchi principales*) *The trachea divides* into two main bronchi : the right and left main bronchi.
- Secondary bronchi – (*lobar bronchi*) *are the bronchi that enter the lobes of* the lungs. There are 3 in the right lung and 2 in the left lung.
- Tertiary bronchi (*segmental bronchi*) are bronchi that carry air to the segments.
- Smaller bronchi and bronchioles ultimately reach the air sacs (alveoli) where the exchange of oxygen and carbon dioxide takes place.

The purpose of the article: The main purpose of this article is to inform the general public, healthcare professionals, and individuals suffering from or at risk of developing chronic bronchitis about the importance of early detection and modern treatment methods. The article covers issues such as identifying the early signs of chronic bronchitis, the benefits of early diagnosis, modern diagnostic methods (including spirometry, etc.), the main areas of early treatment (medication, breathing exercises), the importance of lifestyle in treatment, and the

prevention of complications. The ultimate goal of the article is to provide readers with clear and understandable information about chronic bronchitis, to increase their knowledge of early detection and effective treatment of the disease, and to have a positive impact on their health. Will review in detail the important aspects of early detection of chronic bronchitis, modern diagnostic methods, and effective treatment approaches aimed at preventing the progression of the disease. This information is of great importance in providing timely care to patients with chronic bronchitis and improving their quality of life.

Materials and methods. The main diagnostic method for diagnosing chronic bronchitis is spirometry. *Spirometry* is a lung function test that measures a patient's ability to breathe and the rate at which they can breathe. It can help determine the degree of airway narrowing and obstruction associated with bronchitis. It can also help differentiate chronic bronchitis from other lung conditions, such as asthma or COPD. The patient should refrain from smoking, heavy physical activity, or eating for at least 6-8 hours before the examination. If the patient is taking an inhaler or other medication, the doctor may temporarily stop the medication.

Medical history and symptom assessment - the following signs are noted during the interview with the patient: Cough with phlegm for at least 2 years, 3 months or more each year. Shortness of breath, fatigue, smoking history, exposure to chemicals or dust, these data play an important role in determining the likelihood of the disease.

Results and Discussion. Chronic bronchitis is a chronic diffuse inflammation of the bronchial mucosa. It is characterized by a violation of the cleansing and protective function of the bronchi and constant or periodic cough with sputum, increased thickness and hypersecretion of bronchial secretions, and remodeling of the epithelial structure, without association with other diseases of the bronchial pulmonary system. In contrast to acute bronchitis, chronic bronchitis is called when a patient has cough and sputum for three months a year for at least two years. The most common cause is smoking, which causes the bronchi to become constantly irritated and inflamed in smokers. In addition, polluted air, harmful gases and dust in the workplace, frequent acute infections, hereditary predisposition, living in a cold climate, and reduced immunity can also contribute to the development of the disease. Chronic bronchitis is one of the most common respiratory diseases in the world. The prevalence of chronic bronchitis among different segments of the population is 5-17%. According to data, in 80% of patients with chronic bronchitis, the cause is smoking. The incidence of the disease peaked in 2016, with more than 8.9 million Americans diagnosed with chronic bronchitis, with nearly 75 percent of cases occurring in people over the age of 45 who were chronic smokers.

Forms of chronic bronchitis:

- Normal (non- obstructive)
- Obstructive

1. *Chronic simple (non-obstructive) bronchitis* - characterized by damage to the proximal bronchi and a relatively favorable clinical course and outcome of the disease.

2. *Chronic obstructive bronchitis* - in which deep degenerative- inflammatory and sclerotic changes are observed not only in the proximal, but also in the distal parts of the respiratory tract.

Weight level:

- *Mild* - more than 70% of the forced expiratory volume in one second ;
- *Medium* - forced expiratory volume in one second from 50 to 69%;
- *Severe* - forced expiratory volume in one second is less than 50% of normal

Signs:

- Wheezing – a whistling sound when breathing
- Shortness of breath
- Rapid heartbeat (tachycardia)
- Fatigue

Complications of the disease:

- ✓ Pulmonary emphysema
- ✓ Shortness of breath
- ✓ Bronchiectasis
- ✓ pulmonary arterial hypertension
- ✓ Heart with lungs

Treatment. The main goal of treating chronic bronchitis is to relieve symptoms, slow the progression of the disease, and improve quality of life.

Lifestyle change .

- Quitting smoking is the most important measure . Tobacco smoke irritates the bronchi and aggravates the disease.
- Clean air - you need to stay away from dust, smoke, and other substances harmful to the respiratory tract .

- fatty , sugary foods, and eat foods that boost immunity.

Treatment with medications.

- Broncholytics – dilate the bronchi, making breathing easier. Anti-inflammatory drugs – usually corticosteroids.
- Mucolytics - thin phlegm , making it easier to cough up.
- Antibiotics are only prescribed if there is a bacterial infection .

Physiotherapy and rehabilitation .

- Breathing exercises (such as Buteyko or "belly breathing" techniques).
- Mucolytic inhalations – medications are administered through a nebulizer.

Disease prevention. To prevent chronic bronchitis, it is first necessary to completely quit smoking. Tobacco smoke constantly irritates the bronchi and aggravates the disease. Also, staying away from dust, smoke, chemical gases, frequent ventilation of the room and being in a fresh air environment are beneficial for the respiratory tract. Strengthening immunity is important: proper nutrition, physical activity, sufficient sleep and a stress-free lifestyle should be followed. Annual vaccination against influenza and pneumonia also prevents infections. If a cold, cough or other signs of infection appear, they should be treated in a timely manner.

Conclusion. In conclusion, early detection of chronic bronchitis is important not only in slowing the progression of the disease, but also in significantly improving the overall quality of life of patients and reducing the risk of serious complications, including lung infections, pulmonary hypertension and heart failure. Paying attention to symptoms such as persistent cough, especially cough with sputum production, shortness of breath, wheezing and chest discomfort, which are manifested in the early stages of the disease, as well as being aware of the main risk factors such as smoking, air pollution and exposure to occupational hazards, is the first step towards early diagnosis.

In modern medicine, lung function tests such as spirometry allow the disease to be detected even in its early, latent stages. These tests help to detect airway obstruction early by measuring the volume and speed of inhalation and exhalation. Once diagnosed early, the main goal of treatment is to control symptoms, slow the progression of the disease, and prevent complications. Treatment options include lifestyle changes (quitting smoking, avoiding air pollution and occupational exposures), medications (bronchodilators, anti-inflammatory drugs, and expectorants), and pulmonary rehabilitation programs (exercise, breathing techniques, and psychological support). Regular medical monitoring and strict adherence to the treatment plan are essential to stabilize patients' condition and reduce the negative effects of the disease. Thus, early detection and timely initiation of comprehensive treatment approaches can significantly improve the quality of life of patients living with chronic bronchitis and increase their life expectancy.

References:

1. Usmanov R.Dj. , Mirsharapov U.M ., Tolmasov R.T. "Anatomical structure of internal organs and their blood vessels anatomy" // 2024. С-70.
2. Толмасов Р. Т. и др. ЯЗВНАЯ БОЛЕЗНЬ ЖЕЛУДКА И СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ЕГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ //THE THEORY OF RECENT SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN THE FIELD OF PEDAGOGY. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 22. – С. 342-349.
3. Худойназарова С. Ш., Толмасов Р. Т. ЛЕЧЕНИЕ АРИТМИИ СЕРДЦА В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ МЕДИЦИНЕ И АНАТОМИИ СЕРДЦА //THE THEORY OF RECENT SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN THE FIELD OF PEDAGOGY. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 22. – С. 336-341.

4. Толмасов Р. Т. и др. АНАТОМИЯ ПОЧЕК И СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ РАННЕГО ВЫЯВЛЕНИЯ ПОЧЕЧНО-КАМЕННОЙ БОЛЕЗНИ //THE THEORY OF RECENT SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN THE FIELD OF PEDAGOGY. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 22. – С. 329-335.
5. Tolmasovich T. R. et al. ANATOMY AND METHODS OF TREATMENT OF ULCERATIVE COLITIS IN MODERN MEDICINE //JOURNAL OF APPLIED MEDICAL SCIENCES. – 2024. – Т. 7. – №. 6. – С. 62-70.
6. Tolmasovich T. R. et al. TREATMENT OF MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION IN MODERN MEDICINE //JOURNAL OF MEDICINE AND PHARMACY. – 2024. – Т. 7. – №. 6. – С. 132-138.
7. Tolmasovich T. R. et al. MODERN METHODS AND ANATOMY OF DETERMINING LUNG DISEASES //International journal of medical sciences. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №. 08. – С. 45-50.
8. Толмасов Р. Т., Худойназарова С. Ш. ЛЕЧЕНИЕ АРИТМИИ СЕРДЦА В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ МЕДИЦИНЕ И АНАТОМИИ СЕРДЦА //THE THEORY OF RECENT SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN THE FIELD OF PEDAGOGY. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 22. – С. 354-359.
9. Tolmasov R. T., Jamilova S. K. Causes of Rheumatism and Methods of Treatment in Modern Medicine //American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 8. – С. 102-107.
10. Tolmasovich T. R. et al. ANATOMY AND METHODS OF TREATMENT OF ULCERATIVE COLITIS IN MODERN MEDICINE //JOURNAL OF APPLIED MEDICAL SCIENCES. – 2024. – Т. 7. – №. 6. – С. 62-70.
11. Tolmasovich T. R., Narimon o'g'li T. L. METHODS OF TREATMENT OF CONGENITAL HEART DEFECTS IN MODERN MEDICINE //Western European Journal of Medicine and Medical Science. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 8. – С. 20-26.
12. Tolmasovich T. R. et al. MODERN MEDICAL METHODS OF EARLY DETECTION AND TREATMENT OF KIDNEY STONE DISEASE //JOURNAL OF APPLIED MEDICAL SCIENCES. – 2024. – Т. 7. – №. 6. – С. 55-61.
13. Tolmasovich T. R., Shavkatovna K. S. HEART ARRHYTHMIA DISEASE AND ITS TREATMENT METHODS IN MODERN MEDICINE //JOURNAL OF MEDICINE AND PHARMACY. – 2024. – Т. 7. – №. 6. – С. 139-145.
14. Tolmasovich T. R., Rasulxon o'g'li R. R. STOMACH STRUCTURE AND ITS CHANGES DEPENDING ON AGE //JOURNAL OF MEDICINE AND PHARMACY. – 2024. – Т. 7. – №. 6. – С. 107-112.
15. Tolmasovich T. R., Toxir o'g'li E. S., Maratovich M. O. TREATMENT METHODS AND ANATOMY OF UMBILICAL HERNIA IN MODERN MEDICINE //AMERICAN JOURNAL OF APPLIED MEDICAL SCIENCE. – 2025. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 198-205.
16. Tolmasov R. T. et al. Treatment of Glaucoma in Modern Medicine //American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences. – 2025. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 58-64.
17. Tolmasovich T. R. et al. MODERN METHODS AND ANATOMY OF DETERMINING LUNG DISEASES //Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research. – 2025. – Т. 12. – №. 01. – С. 277-282.
18. Yuldasheva Z. et al. NORMAL YURAK TUZILISHINI YOSHGA OID MOSLASHUV O'ZGARISHLARI //Журнал академических исследований нового Узбекистана. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 34-37.

19. Tolmasovich T. R., Faliddinovich F. S., Jasurbekovich E. P. TREATMENT METHODS AND ANATOMY OF ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE IN MODERN MEDICINE //AMERICAN JOURNAL OF APPLIED MEDICAL SCIENCE. – 2025. – T. 3. – №. 1. – C. 324-331.
20. Tolmasov R. LABORATORY METHODS FOR THE DIAGNOSIS OF UPPER AND LOWER RESPIRATORY TRACT INFECTIONS IN CHILDREN //International journal of medical sciences. – 2025. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 89-93.
21. Tolmasov R. T., Khudoynazarova S. S. OSTEOCHONDROSIS AND ITS TREATMENT METHODS IN MODERN MEDICINE //European Journal of Modern Medicine and Practice. – 2025. – T. 5. – №. 3. – C. 225-231.
22. Tolmasovich T. R., Toxir o‘g‘li E. S., Maratovich M. O. TREATMENT METHODS AND ANATOMY OF UMBILICAL HERNIA IN MODERN MEDICINE //AMERICAN JOURNAL OF APPLIED MEDICAL SCIENCE. – 2025. – T. 3. – №. 1. – C. 198-205.
23. Anvarov M. O. O. G. L., Tolmasov R. Z. T. O‘ZBEKISTON HUDUDIDA KO ‘Z KASALLIKLARI BILAN OG ‘RIGAN BEMORLAR RUHIY HOLATINING DIAGNOSTIKASI VA PSIXOKORREKSIYA USULLARI //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2025. – №. Conference. – C. 131-134.
24. Tolmasov R. et al. AGE-RELATED CHANGES IN STOMACH STRUCTURE DURING PALM OIL FEEDING DURING POSTNATAL ONTOGENESIS //International Journal of Modern Medicine. – 2025. – T. 4. – №. 04. – C. 16-23.
25. Ro‘zibek T. T., Mirsharapov U. M. MORPHOMETRY OF GASTRIC WALL LAYERS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF PALM OIL //Central Asian Journal of Medicine. – 2025. – №. 3. – C. 117-125.
26. Tolmasov R. T. et al. Pancreas Disease-Modern Diabetes Treatment Methods and Anatomy //American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences. – 2025. – T. 3. – №. 4. – C. 132-137.
27. Tolmasov R. T., Shukurov U. M. Modern Treatment Methods of Kidney Structure and Chronic Pyelonephritis //American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences. – 2025. – T. 3. – №. 4. – C. 264-271.
28. Tolmasov R. T. et al. Early Detection and Modern Treatment Methods of Congenital Heart Defect //American Journal of Biomedicine and Pharmacy. – 2025. – T. 2. – №. 5. – C. 46-54.